

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D5.8 – Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making I

WP5 – AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised
Recommendation

Dissemination Level: Public
Document type: Report
Version: 1.0
Date: April 29, 2022

The project iHelp has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for research, technological development, and demonstration under grant agreement no 101017441.

Document Details

Project Number	101017441
Project Title	iHelp - Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records
Title of deliverable	Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making I
Work package	WP5
Due Date	April 30, 2022
Submission Date	April 29, 2022
Start Date of Project	January 1, 2021
Duration of project	36 months
Main Responsible Partner	Information Catalyst (ICE)
Deliverable nature	Report
Author name(s)	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid, Oscar Garcia (ICE), Lars Gustafsson, Fia Andersson, Tanja Tomson (KI)
Reviewer name(s)	Giorgos Giotis, Maritini Kalogerini (ATC), Dr Shabbir Syed Abdul (TMU)

Document Revision History

Version History			
Version	Date	Author(s)	Changes made
0.1	2022-03-07	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid (ICE), Lars Gustafsson, Tanja Tomson (KI)	Table of content, initial version and revision
0.2	2022-04-11	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid (ICE), Fia Andersson (KI) Tanja Tomson (KI)	Revised version
0.3	2022-04-14	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid, Oscar Garcia (ICE)	Revised Version
0.4	2022-04-19	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid (ICE)	Revised Version
0.5	2022-04-21	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid, Oscar Garcia (ICE)	Revised Version
0.6	2022-04-25	Giorgos Giotis, Maritini Kalogerini (ATC)	Comments & 1 st Internal Review
0.7	2022-04-26	Dr Shabbir Syed Abdul (TMU)	Comments & 2 nd Internal Review

0.8	2022-04-27	Usman Rashid, Usman Wajid (ICE)	Revised version based on the internal reviews and comments
0.9	2022-04-28	Pavlos Kranas (LXS)	Quality review
1.0	2022-04-29	Dimosthenis Kyriazis (UPRC)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive summary	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Objectives of Deliverable.....	6
1.2 Document Structure	7
1.3 Relation with other WPs.....	7
2 State of the Art.....	8
3 Overview of Social Media Analyser	9
3.1 Background.....	9
3.2 Purpose of Social Media Analysis in iHelp Project.....	9
3.2.1 Ethical Considerations	10
3.3 User Stories to Guide the Development of the Solution	10
3.3.1 Epic 1 – Application Development	11
3.3.2 Epic 2 – Application Customisation	12
3.3.3 Epic 3 – Application Results.....	13
3.4 Policy Evaluation Scenario.....	14
4 Architecture Design.....	16
4.1 Technologies used for implementation of Architecture	16
4.2 Implementation of the Architecture	17
5 User Interface for the Social Analyser Solution.....	19
5.1 Login Screen.....	19
5.2 Applications List.....	19
5.3 Application Details.....	20
5.4 Creating Application	20
5.5 Defining Rules and Conditions.....	21
5.6 Alerts Lists.....	22
5.7 Alert Information.....	22
6 Expected Results	24
6.1 Potential Role in Policy Making	24
7 Conclusion	25
Bibliography	26
List of Acronyms.....	27

Table of Figures

- Figure 1: Policy Assessment Scenario..... 15
- Figure 2: Social Media Analyser – User Design. 16
- Figure 3: Overview of Social Analyser Component Architecture. 17
- Figure 4: Implementation of Architecture. 18
- Figure 5: Login Screen. 19
- Figure 6: Applications list. 20
- Figure 7: Application Details. 20
- Figure 8: Creating Application..... 21
- Figure 9: Rules & Conditions. 21
- Figure 10: Alerts List..... 22
- Figure 11: Alert Information..... 23

Executive summary

The ubiquity of smart phones and other mobile devices, make it easy to instantly and broadly share experiences on social media such as Facebook, Twitter etc. As the number of users on social media sites continues to increase, so does the need for health policy planner to monitor ongoing discussions to assist in provision of public health and service. The analysis of data can provide useful insight into the social trends and societal perception about healthcare policies. In this background, social media analytics is concerned with developing and evaluating informatics tools and frameworks to collect, monitor, analyse, summarize, and visualize social media data ... to gather social trends, societal insight and useful patterns from certain topics of interest.

Within the iHelp project, the T5.4 (“Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making”) focuses on supporting the health-related policy makers in their activities concerning the analysis of existing policies as well as the design of better or more focused health related policies or health services. To support the policy makers, a social media analysis tool is being developed in the project with the view to investigate societal views on specific topics of interest. This tool will enable the policy makers to gather real-time or near real-time data from social media platform concerning health policies and health services. The gathered data will be analysed within the tool using advanced data analytic techniques (such as complex event processing). The results of the analysis will be provided to the policy makers through an intuitive interface, allowing them to study the level of awareness, social attitudes towards prevention programs/health services, and general perceptions about different topics such as cancer related risks, risk related factors, existing healthcare programs etc.

This deliverable provides an overview of the social media analysis tool, starting from the technical requirements and user scenarios that are taken into account to develop the architecture of the tool and the mock-ups of the different interfaces that the tool will offer the users. The mock-ups cover the different user interactions scenarios enabled and supported by the tool and provides an idea of how the developed functionalities can serve the different needs of the target users.

Based on this background work, the development of an early prototype is reported in this deliverable. The deliverable concludes with the description of expected role of the tool in the policy making activities and the future work planned in the respective task of the iHelp project.

1 Introduction

In this age of social connectivity, lifestyle behaviours, opinions and attitudes are shared and discussed openly among large groups of people on different social media platforms. This continuous exchange of views impacts society as it could lead to building a general perception about a specific topic or issue that may further develop consensus irrespective of whether it is true or not. It is therefore of importance to policy makers to keep updated about the public discourse taking place online in order to evaluate existing policies but also to effectively create new policy.

This deliverable presents a case for a possibility of realising the need of exploring Social Media Analytics and its growing role of importance to the policy making process regarding health care, public health, and prevention.

The study of societal factors and lifestyle patterns could help developing or improving the policy making process. In this age of social connectivity, lifestyles and views are shared and discussed openly among large groups of people. This continuous exchange of views could lead to building a general perception about a specific topic/issue and can further develop a consensus irrespective of whether it is true or not.

According to studies, in 2019 one in every 14 searches on Google were in relation to health issues and there were 70,000 searches per minute. In a US study published in 2019, for instance, in the 7 days prior to an Emergency Department (ED) visit, the percentage of health-related searches by patients was 15%, as against the more standard 6%. During that time, 56% of patients searched for symptoms, 53% for information about a hospital and 23% about the treatment or management of a disease. 53% of participants who used Google in the week leading up to their ED visit searched for content directly related to their chief complaint. Similarly, in a 2018 Australian study, 49% of patients reported regularly searching the Internet for health information and 34.8% had searched regarding their current health problem before presenting at an ED, prompting the authors to conclude that 'searching had a positive impact on the doctor-patient interaction and was unlikely to reduce adherence to treatment.

Despite the above-mentioned stats, further studies and research done in this regard show that social media is underused in evaluating intervention in health research. The use of social media within a mixed-method approach for developing and evaluating interventions could yield actionable insights. Therefore, the development of a Social Media Analyser tool within the scope of iHelp project was proposed. The idea is to harness the social media streams from multiple platforms and extract meaningful data for specific topics of interest i.e. Pancreatic Cancer. This data will be analysed, and results will be displayed for the policy maker to draw conclusions that may assist in policy making process. The results may also help in understanding the impact of any existing policy and could provide a continuous loop of feedback in understanding the overall perception of the policy/interventions disseminated to the public.

1.1 Objectives of Deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to explain the Social Media Analyser tool as a solution designed and developed to address the objectives set out in this task when the project was conceived. This document will present the progress of this tool in line with the objectives realised in the DoA. As the Social Media Analyser tool is a standalone component working in sort of isolation from the rest of the project architecture, this deliverable aims to highlight the value that will added to the project by this tool.

The use of social media platforms has increased unprecedently, enabling the opportunity for the public engagement with social media to provide relevant first-hand information about the health interventions. Therefore, researchers around the world are using the data extracted from these platforms as a contributing factor to the results of their research.

This deliverable aims to provide a scope of the social media analyser tool as an effective intervention to map the different uses of social media for health research purposes.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1** – An introduction including defining the objective and relation to other WPs in the project
- **Section 2** – This section presents an overview of the of the social media analyser tool with its background technology, purpose, and role. It also presents some user stories for understanding its functionality and how this tool could help in developing, evaluating or improving policies
- **Section 3** – This section overviews the architecture design of this component and its implementation in the project
- **Section 4** – Section 4 presents an overview of the user interface with brief explanation of its functionality
- **Section 5** – This section discusses the expected results achieved from this tool in the defined scope of project and how it could play a potential role in policy making.

1.3 Relation with other WPs

The social analyser tool primarily is a standalone component that exists within the architecture of iHelp. This tool does not have a significant relation with any of the other WPs. However, it does collaborate with the T4.3 (“DSS Suite with Visual Analytic Tools”) as the DSS suite may be used to display the visual results. As the Social Media Analyser tool extracts data from the social media and store it in HHR database.

2 State of the Art

Research shows that social media has become a major source of health information. Around 80% of adult internet users report seeking some form of health information online. This unprecedented rise of social media use has allowed the emergence of the following concepts:

- Infodemiology – is an area of science research focused on scanning the internet for user-contributed health-related content, with the ultimate goal of improving public health
- Infoveillance – is a type of syndromic surveillance that specifically utilizes information found online

The more traditional method of extracting data from the social media platforms includes a keyword search technique from archived posts from public databases available e.g. Web of Science (WOS) Database and apply manual analysis to further refine the data to obtain meaningful outcomes.

With the increasing use of study concepts i.e. Infodemiology and Infoveillance, opportunities were realised to develop new methodologies in health research to overcome the limitations in the traditional methods. Furthermore, due to the vast amount, dynamics, and complexity of these data, early efforts to evaluate engagement in group-based social media interventions have typically relied on either high-level summary of usage i.e., number of page hits, time spent on a page, multiple Social Media Analysis tools have been developed and available in the commercial sector to provide solutions to harness the information flow on these platforms.

All social media platforms e.g. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Reddit etc provide a dashboard for its users to analyse the impact of the posts and content. However, these tools are focused on business community and assist in monitoring the outreach and impact of the dissemination of information through social media. These tools rely heavily on the activity and engagement of the users which may provide a limited scope of gathering relevant information. Using a similar approach, healthcare and policy making professionals use these tools to understand the impact of the information disseminated and build further strategies to maximise its impact. Although, this strategy has been somewhat effective and providing information of significant importance, it has limitations in providing a holistic view of the intervention that may assist the policy maker to improve on existing or create a new policy.

The social media analyser tool developed in iHelp is conceived and developed specifically to provide the tool within the architecture and framework of this project. The objective is to overcome the limitations in the commercially available tools and allow the policy maker to design bespoke applications within the system to focus on specific topics of interest. The User Interface and process flow has been designed, in light of the discussions and feedback of clinicians participating In this project, to make it convenient and an easy-to-use solution for the policy maker.

3 Overview of Social Media Analyser

The Social media Analyser is a tool developed by employing latest technologies, as explained in Section 4.1 of this deliverable, to provide or further improve a toolkit for clinicians and policy makers for collecting, analysing, visualising, and storing data from multiple social media platforms to grasp what social media discussions related to public health and health ongoing among the public.

3.1 Background

ICE developed a Social Media Analysis solution in the EC funded Red-Alert project (Grant agreement ID: 740688) using state of art technologies. It allows creating and running multiple applications with specific conditions for extracting social media information concerning specific topics and generating alerts when information exchanges concerning the specific topics of interest are detected for each application. The Complex Event Processing (CEP) functionality is employed in this solution to analyse social media posts about specific topics of interest such as, terrorism. The overall functionality of this solution is supported by Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Social Network Analysis (SNA) techniques.

The solution uses individual social media APIs to extract the social media posts according to the conditions or topics of interest defined in the applications. The data analysis techniques like NLP (extraction of concepts, sentiment, topics, etc.) and SNA (relations between users) are implemented to these posts to obtain insights from the social media.

This background is being enhanced in the iHelp project with the aim to analyse the data from multiple social media platforms. The solution will be able to process batch (social media) data shared by the users, which may come from one of the various social networks i.e. Twitter, Facebook, Reddit. Moreover, the NLP, Sentiment Analysis (SA), SNA and other data analytic and visualisation techniques will be revamped to be able to process different types of data and support the different types (e.g. policy evaluation, policy definition etc) of needs in the iHelp project.

3.2 Purpose of Social Media Analysis in iHelp Project

Research suggest that social media analysis can be a powerful tool to support decision making. Based on the results achieved in Red-Alert EU Project, it is validated that this activity could provide quantifiable decision support e.g. to support health related policy making and assessment in iHelp. Within the iHelp project, the information gathered from this tool can help analyse the social and societal trends towards existing healthcare practices, health related policies, the need for more focused policies and in particularly the policies that can be considered as related to cancer.

The use of social media has grown massively over the last few years. According to Statista, over 3.6 billion people were using social media worldwide in 2020, a number projected to increase to almost 4.41 billion in 2025. A prominent social media platform like Twitter has garnered the attention of 329 million users in 2022, with an expectancy to rise to 340.2 million users by 2024. With an exceptional growth in these micro-blogging sites, user interact or share their opinion about a plethora of topics from all walks of life.

The social media analysis tool in the iHelp project will help the policy makers understand the opinions of social media users and reveal the sentiment towards specific healthcare policies and the user satisfaction with existing healthcare practices. The tool will be able to calculate attributes such as sentiments and also polarity, and subjectivity from the social media streams and provide the healthcare policy makers with

insight into lifestyle trends, mental models, emotions, social interactions, and societal influences on the individuals. Access to this type of information would enable the policy makers to gauge the impact of existing policies and have actionable data from people who either can benefit from more targeted and impactful policies. In this respect, the social media analysis tool will support the evaluation of existing policies or to help design new/better policies that address the emerging healthcare needs. With a closer understanding of social media users, policy makers will be able to predict the need for, evaluate and design policies in order to address and prevent emerging health care needs.

3.2.1 Ethical Considerations

As the social media analyser tool will be engaging with the content posted by the social media users on different social media platforms, it is important that the data is consumed with the appropriate ethical considerations in place. According to the terms of service of the social media platforms, the users allow the social media platform a worldwide, non-exclusive, royalty-free license (with the right to sublicense) to use, copy, reproduce, process, adapt, modify, publish, transmit, display, and distribute such Content in any and all media or distribution methods now known or later developed (for clarity, these rights include, for example, curating, transforming, and translating). This license authorises to make user content available to the rest of the world and to let others do the same. In this respect, there are currently no restrictions on the use or reuse of information that is broadcasted on the social media platforms.

Furthermore, T5.4 leaders have surveyed the GSR Ethical Assurance for Social and Behavioural Research guidance document and considered the core principles for conducting a social media research. Table 1 below shows a breakdown of the core principles, and the engagement of social media analyser tool in consideration of these principles.

Table 1: Core principles for conducting a social media research

Core Principle	Engagement
Sound application and conduct of social research methods, and interpretation of the findings	The social media analyser tool employs appropriate and professional methods to conduct research. The research is conducted on the data available in public domain and no sensitive or personal data is taken into consideration. The outcomes of this research will be available publicly for further research purposes
Participation based on informed consent	The task does not require users of social media platforms to participate but uses the publicly available data, which is allowed to use and process, as per the terms of services agreed by the users
Enabling participation	Social media analyser tool does not focus on inclusion or exclusion of any groups of people but rely on focussing on specific areas/topics of interest which are discussed among all groups of users
Avoidance of personal and social harm	Social media analyser tool does not engage with any sensitive data to avoid any possibility of personal or social harm.
Non-disclosure of identity	Although the social media analyser tool may collect data from specific users however, the identity of the users will not be disclosed and only the outcomes of research will be shared in public domain.

3.3 User Stories to Guide the Development of the Solution

A user story is an informal, natural language description of a software system's features. User stories are written by and/or from the perspective of an end-user to help design/develop a solution according to user

needs. The scope of a user story is typically defined to facilitate ease of understanding for the development teams and serve as a basis for communication.

Example: As a <user_role>, I want <desired_action> so that <receive_benefit>

The user story is composed of three parts as highlighted (in different colours) in the example above. User story is completed by an 'Acceptance Criteria' for verification of the implemented features.

Example of Acceptance Criteria: "Capability to search for and retrieve results according to indicated parameters."

To help guide the development of the Social Media Analyser tool in the iHelp project, the user stories are categorised into three epics with specific user stories to explain the user experience

Table 2 - Summary of Epics

No	Epic Name	User Stories
1	Application Development	Logging in to System
		Creating New Application
		Status of Existing Applications
2	Application Customisation	Review Application
		Fine Tune and App Customisation
3	Application Results	Collect and Store information
		Analysis & Presentation of information

To understand the user stories, the events are grouped under different epics as discussed in the sections below.

3.3.1 Epic 1 – Application Development

This epic encompasses the user journey of logging in the system, reviewing the existing applications and creating a new one.

3.3.1.1 US1 – Logging in to System

Short Description:

- As a Policy Maker, I want to access the tool

Acceptance Criteria:

- Providing credentials to the users
- Ability to login to system through secure authentication

Fulfilment:

The secure authentication system allows the user to log in to the SM Analyser tool with the unique credentials (username/password) provided by the system administrator

3.3.1.2 US2 – Creating New Application

Short Description:

- As a policy maker, I want to create a new application in the tool

Acceptance Criteria:

- Ability to start building a new application
- Interface where user can define a name for the application
- Name and provide short description of the application
- Choose the preferred SM platform and Language
- Upload Keywords list file
- Add new individual keywords in the list

Fulfilment:

User will create a new application by using the applied functionality in the dashboard after logging in to the tool and have the option of specifying the name and short description about the functionality. They will be allowed to choose a particular SM platform and the language of interest. There is a provision to upload two separate keyword files along with the ability to add new keywords individually.

3.3.1.3 US3 – Status of Existing Applications

Short Description:

- As a policy maker, I want to see the status of existing applications

Acceptance Criteria:

- List of existing applications with their status
- Ability to Start, Pause or Stop an application

Fulfilment:

The user is able to have an overview of the existing applications with their current status. Users are able to perform actions on a particular application.

3.3.2 Epic 2 – Application Customisation

This epic describes the user journey of application definition, reviewing and applying the conditions and rules to extract focused information from the social media platform.

3.3.2.1 US4 – Review Application

Short Description:

- As a policy maker, I want to (re)view the application created in the system

Acceptance Criteria:

- Visibility of application details
 - Date of creation
 - Starting date
 - Status
 - Number of alerts generated
- Action buttons to start, stop or pause the application

- List of keywords and ability to add more keywords

Fulfilment:

Users will be able to review the application details and will be able to perform certain actions to the application. The list of applied keywords will be visible with a function to update with new keywords.

3.3.2.2 US5 – Fine Tune and App Customisation

Short Description:

- As a policy maker, I want to fine tune my existing application for specific topics

Acceptance Criteria:

- Ability to define rules and conditions for the application.
- Ability to create a nested condition instance using the two keyword lists within a specific frame of time
- Ability to define the application based on 'And/Or' rule within a specific context

Fulfilment:

User will be able to define (nested) conditions using the keyword lists uploaded in a previous scenario, within a specific range of time. They can further focus the application by adding customisation using 'And/Or' rule in the context of a specific topic. This will allow the system to generate alerts based on the defined conditions and rules.

3.3.3 Epic 3 – Application Results

This epic describes the user stories how the applications in the tool extract the information and how the results are displayed for understanding.

3.3.3.1 US6 – Collect and Store Information

Short Description:

- As a policy maker, I want to collect, visualise, and store information gathered by the application

Acceptance Criteria:

- System is able to collect, collate and visualise the information based on the rules defined in applications
- The list of alerts generated is stacked in a matrix with key information and time
- The number of alerts generated, number of apps running will be visualised for information
- A graph will be plotted showing these generated alerts vs applications over time

Fulfilment:

Based on the rules and conditions defined in the application, the user will be able to see visualised results generated, with information that triggered the alert through the application where these conditions and rules are being defined. They will be able to see the alerts generated and the running applications. There will be a graph showing the number of alerts being generated in time.

3.3.3.2 US7 – Analysis & Presenting Information

Short Description:

- As a Policy Maker, I would like to see detailed information of any generated alert

Acceptance Criteria:

- System should display the details of the alert generated and following attributes should be identified. It is important to note that this level of detailed analysis is only developed in the iHelp project.
 - Time of SM post
 - Polarity scale
 - Subjectivity scale
 - Sentiment i.e., Positive, Negative, Neutral
 - Trigger word
- System should present information about the posts from the selected SM User, present a count and the show the number of running applications generated the alerts along with a graph showing the aggregated alerts during the day.

Fulfilment:

The user will be able to see a detailed analysis of the alerts generated for a particular SM user account. The algorithms will show an in-depth analysis of the posts generated in a specific time scale presenting several sentimental attributes.

3.4 Policy Evaluation Scenario

The different applications designed in the social media analyser tool work in collaboration with each other to provide a holistic societal scenario of the general sentiment based on lifestyle, trends, and patterns. The idea is to execute multiple applications focusing on specific topics to achieve results to build a scenario that will assist in improving existing or creating new policy.

An example scenario is explained in figure 1 below. This scenario explains how different applications work together in the tool to extract the required information and draw conclusions that may assist in building a new policy or improving on to the existing ones.

There are three applications working in this scenario. Each application is generating 50 alerts for the chosen keywords and an overall sentiment is calculated based on these alerts.

Application 1 is filtering the social media posts for keywords (Screening program, Pancreatic Cancer). This application would generate alerts with the two keywords and the Sentiment Network Analysis component would provide an overall sentiment regarding these keywords. In this case, the overall sentiment is negative.

Similarly, Application 2 scans the social media posts for keywords i.e. Screening Program, Cancer and the overall sentiment is positive. While the Application 3 is scanning the social media posts for the keyword i.e. Cancer Treatment and the overall sentiment is positive.

Figure 1: Policy Assessment Scenario.

Based on the outcomes from the three applications the policy maker gets the following outcomes.

- The general sentiment regarding the screening of Pancreatic Cancer is negative
- People are either dissatisfied or are unaware of the screening programs for Pancreatic Cancer
- People are aware or satisfied about the screening program for Cancer in general
- People are aware or satisfied with the Cancer treatment provided

The conclusion from this scenario provides a case for the policy makers to review the prevalent policies. The outcome from the Applications highlights the need of awareness activities and effective information dissemination for the Pancreatic Cancer screening program. As the other outcomes from the other applications suggest that people are generally happy with the treatment, information or screening programs for Cancer, this scenario assists the policy makers to improve on the policy for Pancreatic Cancer.

4 Architecture Design

The architecture of the Social Analyser solution incorporates several sub-components, each with a specific purpose that contributes towards delivering a comprehensive social media analysis and decision support system.

The solution is composed of a set of Docker containers (representing different sub-components such as NLP, SA, SNA, etc) that communicate and process data gathered through Apache Kafka, which is responsible for orchestrating data gathered from the social media platform(s). Each set of containers start with a Social Media Source that is outputted to Kafka. The data from Kafka is passed through other containers that perform SNA, SA and NLP before the data is ready for processing through the Complex Event Processing (CEP) containers. Each CEP container will have its own (data analysis) rules to process data concerning specific topics of interest. Alerts are generated by the CEP when certain rules are triggered. The alerts are stored and then displayed to the user through the visualisations on the GUI generated by Apache Superset.

Figure 2: Social Media Analyser – User Design.

4.1 Technologies used for implementation of Architecture

- **Complex Event Processing Engine** to develop event patterns and event trends based on expert and machine learning methodologies. The engine will be extended to enable the inference of probabilistic events suitable for early risk identification and evaluation of targeted recommendations.
- **Natural Language Processing** to analyse, decipher, understand, and make sense of the human languages in a manner that is useful for the objectives of the Social Analyser component
- **Sentiment Analysis** to determine whether a given text contains negative, positive, or neutral emotions. It's a form of text analytics that uses NLP and machine learning.

- **Social Network Analysis** to analyse the network of users who are interested in the same topic of discussion or help propagate information concerning the same or similar topic
- **Administrative Dashboard** to create alerts by specifying which topics (keywords and phrases) they are interested in monitoring on specific social media platforms. These topics can relate to the lifestyle trends, mental models, emotional intelligence, social interactions, and societal influences on the individuals
- **Monitoring Dashboard** to provide real-time monitoring updates on the pre-specified alerts through a set of intuitive visualisations. The alerts will show e.g., how many social media posts are being posted on specific topic(s), from whom, when and the pattern of posts
- **ClickHouse** is an open-source column-oriented DBMS for online analytical processing that allows users to generate analytical reports using SQL queries in real-time.
- **Apache Kafka** is a system to manage the events' logs. It is a durable messaging system that send messages between processes, applications, and servers. Apache Kafka is used as a message brokering system in the social media analysis component. It is where the messages will be published for processing by different components in the social media analysis solution.
- **Apache ZooKeeper** is a centralized service for maintaining configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization, and providing group services. ZooKeeper is used to coordinate and manage different components in the social media analysis solution

Figure 3: Overview of Social Analyser Component Architecture.

4.2 Implementation of the Architecture

The Social Media Analyser solution comprises of the state of art technology components working together in a complex collaboration to achieve the outcomes. It provides a system where the user can create a Ruleset (a set of details and rules to get data from social media) and then run these Rulesets to get data based on the details and rules defined by the User.

The user will interact with the tool using an application interface after logging in through a secure authentication system. The application interface will allow the user to design new applications with specific ruleset using a Generator API. These applications are stored in a secure File Storage system. The application interface allows the users to upload multiple keywords file using an uploader API and save it in the File Storage.

Each ruleset created on the GUI is made up of several containers working together where the data is passed between containers using Apache Kafka as a flow.

- The Social Media Container polls a set number of messages after a set amount of time from the Social Media source. This container checks the selected user timeline at an interval of 5 minutes and forward to the sentiment container for calculations.
- The Sentiment Container calculates the sentiment from the text of the message and adds the sentiment, polarity, and subjectivity values
- The CEP container checks the condition defined through the parameters and if the condition passes, an event is created using that data and that event is sent to the next container

The CEP Output compiles all the events that have fulfilled all the conditions and output it to two different topics: a topic containing all alerts and a topic containing all events. From here, all the alerts and events are stored in Clickhouse and can then be displayed in the Social Media Analyser or in Superset as Charts and Graphs.

Figure 4: Implementation of Architecture.

5 User Interface for the Social Analyser Solution

To help guide the development of the Social Analyser solution in the iHelp project, a detailed description of the user interface and its functionality was submitted in the D2.8 – User Centric Design document. This section provides an overview of the different functionalities and relevant user interfaces for the social analyser solution. Based on these design and functional guidelines, the ongoing development activities are currently focusing on realising these design and functional aspects.

5.1 Login Screen

This is the main entry screen for the social analyser solution. The user logs in to the system using a unique username and password created by the systems administrator. The functionality is completed by a secure authentication system.

A wireframe diagram of the iHelp login screen. At the top center is the text "iHelp". Below it are two input fields: the first is labeled "Username" and the second is labeled "Password". To the right of the "Password" field is a "Login" button with a small red arrow pointing to the right.

Figure 5: Login Screen.

5.2 Applications List

After the user is logged in, the user will reach the Applications List screen. This screen summarises the number of existing applications on the social media analyser tool, with a list of options that are available to the users in order to examine each application or to create a new application. User can navigate into a specific application detail or go to the rules screen to edit or review the rules defined for the application.

The user is also provided with the ability to start, stop, or pause an application using the action button provided in the interface

Figure 6: Applications list.

5.3 Application Details

This part of the tool allows the user to review the details of a particular application and the alerts triggered. It provides basic details of the application and allows the user to perform different actions on the application. This screen also shows the keywords uploaded as two separate lists when the application was created. The user is also able to add/append/delete the keywords or topics that the application is monitoring on the social media platforms.

Figure 7: Application Details.

5.4 Creating Application

The user can create a new application to monitor specific topics of interest on a particular social media platform. The application name and description are defined, and the preferred social media platform is selected. Two separate lists of keywords in MS Excel CSV format can be uploaded into the system. The keywords are shown in two separate lists as shown in the image below. User can also add new keywords separately in the lists.

Application List
Users
Create Application

Create Application to Monitor a specific topic on Social Media

General

Application Description

Social Media Source

Twitter
 Facebook
 Reddit

Language English

1st Keywords list Choose File 1st File of Keyword

2nd Keywords list Choose File 2nd File of Keywords

Input Keywords for List 1

Keyword 1
 Keyword 2
 Keyword 3
 Keyword 4

Edit

Input Keywords for List 2

Keyword 1
 Keyword 2
 Keyword 3
 Keyword 4

Edit

Submit Application

Figure 8: Creating Application.

5.5 Defining Rules and Conditions

The application allows the user to define specific conditions and rules in view of the uploaded keywords, to achieve focused results for the application. The user will be able to dictate how the data gathered from this application will be analysed and what information will be extracted. They will be able to create a nested condition instance using a combination of keyword strings to allow the application to extract meaningful insights.

Furthermore, the user will define some rules for keywords. This will determine that the data is extracted when specific keywords appear in a specific context.

Application List
Users
Create Application

Rules for <Application>

Condition 1 If Post contains Keywords List 1

followed by

Condition 2 If previous Post contains Keywords List 2 within 12 hours ✕

+ Add Condition

Custom Rules

Health Appearing 2

And

Treatment Appearing 1

Fallen to the context of Cancer

Save Rules

Figure 9: Rules & Conditions.

5.6 Alerts Lists

This part of the Social Media Analyser shows the alerts generated by a specific application created in the system. Once the ruleset is defined, the posts are scanned from the Social Media platform timeline and alerts are generated when a post is met with the conditions. The alerts are identified in a matrix table with the details. A graph is representing the trend of generating alerts over a period of time along with a numeric count of the total alerts generated by the application running in the system.

The user can navigate into specifics of a particular alert by using the links provided in the matrix table.

Figure 10: Alerts List.

5.7 Alert Information

The Alert information section of the social media analyser tool describes the detailed view of a particular alert e.g., describing the social media messages that triggered the alert, the actual keywords that matched with the keyword list provided by the user, the information about the underlying users, as well as the polarity and subjectivity rating of the alert calculated by the social media analyser tool.

An overarching picture of where this alert fits within the other alerts generated by the running applications, the wireframe also illustrates a summarised view of all the alerts that are generated by the running applications.

Applications
Users
Create Application

Alert ID 1 Information

Tweet 1		Tweet 2	
Time	Mon Mar 14 15:36:04 +0000 2022	Time	Mon Mar 14 15:37:04 +0000 2022
Text	"Health issues" https://t.co/Qu7171JOOz	Text	The treatment is successful
Polarity	0.0	Polarity	0.8
Subjectivity	0.0	Subjectivity	0.6
Positive/Negative	neutral	Positive/Negative	positive
Trigger	"Cancer" IN "Post-1"	Trigger	"Treatment" IN "Post-2"
Context		Context	

User Information - <USER_ID>

User Alert Count
8

User App Count
4

Applications	Total	Today
App 1	3	2
App 2	2	1
App 3	1	0
App 4	2	1

User Alerts

Tweet Text	Positive/Negative	Polarity	Subjectivity	Keyword	Time	App ID	Alert ID
"Health issues" https://t.co/Qu7171JOOz	neutral	0	0	keyword	Wed Jun 16 15:36:04 +0000 2021	App1	1
The treatment is successful https://t.co/qiZIEacFtA	negative	-0.4	0.4	keyword	Wed Jun 16 15:37:04 +0000 2021	App1	2
"productivity" https://t.co/Qu7171JOOz	neutral	0	0	keyword	Wed Jun 16 15:57:04 +0000 2021	App1	1
Game of the year all over again https://t.co/qiZIEacFtA	negative	-0.4	0.4	keyword	Wed Jun 16 15:59:04 +0000 2021	App1	5

Back to App list

Alerts List

Figure 11: Alert Information.

6 Expected Results

The social media analyser solution is expected to provide a detailed insight and engagement into the general public opinion regarding the policies that influence the general health of the population and the existing practices of the healthcare programs.

6.1 Potential Role in Policy Making

The analysis of social media content has the potential of bringing policy makers and the general public closer together. The sentiments and opinions of social media users lends policy makers the potential to current updates of relevant needs and concerns in relation to prevention and treatment. The social media analyser tool will complement the policy makers in analysing a policy or developing a new one. The tool provides societal insights, highlighting the lifestyle trends and patterns of the people discourse on social media. The policy makers can consult these insights in designing a new policy or to measure the impact of an existing policy.

As this solution is the core focus of the T5.4, the partners involved, and a few brainstorming sessions were conducted to identify the stakeholders. This allowed the partners to elaborate the user stories for better understanding. The identified stakeholders are as below:

- Policy Maker – This could be the Local Area/Regional health Representative, Head of department in a major hospital, Patient representative organisation
- Clinician – Medical practitioners who would be using the Social Analyser tool to extract meaningful data
- Patient – People who are either diagnosed with Pancreatic Cancer or are at high risk
- Other Entities – Health Charities, Patients Associations

During the brainstorming sessions, the participants discussed the capability of this tool and realised its role in countering propaganda and fake information about a health policy or other interventions. This would provide an opportunity to understand an overall public sentiment and allow the policy makers to gauge the impact of their policies. It will further enable the policy makers to design better and effective dissemination activities to counter any fake information prevalent in the society.

The social media analyser tool may have far-reaching impact and could be seen as a public asset for betterment of public health policy. There should be published documentation about how it conducts the search and analyse data. Making it open access would allow others to use it for benchmarking, analysis, and further development. The recommendation is to release the tool as an opensource resource with a flexibility of modification, so that it can be used in other industries. This would be a contribution of the iHelp project with a global outreach.

7 Conclusion

The social media analyser solution being developed in the iHelp project has the potential to complement policy making activities as it decreases the distance between policy maker and societal actors or social media users. The data captured from the social media platforms can provide a good assessment of the societal attitudes and sentiments concerning specific topics shared online. As society becomes increasingly more digitalized it is important for policy makers to follow in the same direction and make use of the opportunity to tune in to opinions shared in a social media context. The social media analyser solution developed in the iHelp project can be seen as a start towards integrating real time communication from individuals and cancer patients through social media to health care professionals and policy makers. Alongside the potential benefits of a social media analyser solution, such as curbing effects of disinformation of health information, there are also certain problems or risks that should be considered, for example that trends on social media might not represent the sentiments of the general public.

A social media analyser solution that is available in the public domain can be helpful for researchers and health policy planners to understand to what extent incorrect information on public health issues are generated, discussed and spread in social media. This can help policy makers to inform with solid data on such issues by establishing and promoting evidence-based web sites for health information.

The social media solution is currently being developed, with an initial prototype current available based on the design guidelines discussed in this document. Future work on this solution will involve the complete implementation of the technical and design specifications, together with the demonstrations and validations in real world scenarios.

Bibliography

I. R. Freckelton, "Internet disruptions in the doctor–patient relationship", *Medical Law Review*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 502-525, 2020.

S. Fox, and M. Duggan, "Pew internet and American life project: health online 2013", *Washington: California HealthCare Foundation*, 2013.

H. Korda, and Z. Itani, "Harnessing social media for health promotion and behavior change", *Health promotion practice*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 15-23, 2013.

L. C. Smit, et al, "Value of social network analysis for developing and evaluating complex healthcare interventions: a scoping review". *BMJ open*, vol. 10, no. 11, e039681.

Social Media Reseach Group. "Using social media for social research: An introduction", 2016. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/524750/GSR_Social_Media_Research_Guidance_-_Using_social_media_for_social_research.pdf/. Accessed on March 2022.

Statista. "Number of social media users 2025 | Statista", 2020. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/278414/number-of-worldwide-social-network-users/>. Accessed on March 2022.

Twitter. "Twitter Terms of Service", 2021. <https://twitter.com/en/tos>. Accessed on March 2022.

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEP	Complex Event Processing
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DBMS	Database Management Systems
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
ED	Emergency Department
EU	European Union
HHR	Holistic Health Record
M	Month
NLP	Natural Language Processing
SA	Sentiment Analysis
SNA	Social Network Analysis
SQL	Structured Query Language
T	Task
UC	Use Case
WOS	Web of Science
WP	Work Package